

Workflow and Example Dataset for Python-Based Stitching of Confocal Zebrafish Images from VAST BiImager-Based Screening

Introduction to the VAST-SDCM platform

Over the past two decades, the zebrafish has emerged as an excellent vertebrate model for studying human diseases and toxicology. Zebrafish larvae offer a cost-effective tool for large-scale *in vivo* chemical screening, thanks to their unique advantages compared to other vertebrate models: small size, transparency, large clutches, rapid development, genetic tractability, major organs and disease-related genes shared with humans, and measurable behaviour.

Visualization and imaging of most zebrafish organs requires manual manipulation and appropriate orientation of the animals. Several methods have currently been used to address these challenges, including manually orienting the embryos in viscous media (methyl cellulose) or immobilizing them in low-melting agarose or agarose wells. In some cases, the embryos are fixed with paraformaldehyde for imaging, but fixed animals cannot be used for subsequent studies. These complex handling processes are slow and not ideal for high-content screens. A pivotal technological advancement was the development of the Vertebrate Automated Screening Technology (VAST) BiImager system, which automatically manipulates 2- to 5-day-old sedated zebrafish larvae for imaging (Pardo-Martin et al., 2010; Chang et al., 2012), reducing the time required for these steps by half compared to the manual method (Oprîşoreanu, 2022).

To streamline loading, the Large Particle Sampler (LPS, Union Biometrica, MA, USA) was integrated with VAST, enabling the automated transfer of embryos from 96-well plates and eliminating manual handling. This setup reduces labour-intensive steps while preserving larvae viability for further testing. The VAST BiImager and LPS were combined with the Zeiss Cell Observer Spinning Disk Confocal Microscopic System (SDCM) (Early et al., 2018), referred to as the VAST-SDCM platform (Figure 1). The LPS transfers the larvae to the VAST glass capillary, positioned under the SDCM objective. The system then centres and rotates the capillary to the user-defined orientation, either manually or automatically, followed by confocal image acquisition and/or brightfield imaging with the VAST on-board camera. Once imaged, embryos can be recovered into a 96-well plate for subsequent studies.

Figure 1. VAST-SDCM platform at the Center for Regenerative Therapies Dresden (CRTD). This automated, high-resolution, in vivo screening platform for zebrafish was originally established by the Lyons Lab (Early et al., 2018). The original setup is in the UK Zebrafish Imaging and Screening Facility at the University of Edinburgh.

Imaging

The VAST-SDCM platform can be used for manual, low-throughput confocal imaging, effectively using the VAST system only for loading and positioning of larvae. This imaging mode is used to establish imaging conditions, identify regions of interest, and image the same structure from different angles, thanks to the 360° rotation capabilities of the capillary.

The automated imaging mode of the VAST-SDCM combines the *Time Series* module of the ZEN software for z-stack acquisition, and the *External imaging* mode of the VAST BioImager software. The two software are not integrated, but communicate via Transistor-Transistor Logic (TTL) commands. The VAST BioImager software allows tile acquisition by detecting the tip of the head of the larvae and moving the microscope stage along the x-axis to align the microscope objective to a position pre-established by the user. Then, the TTL signal triggers ZEN acquisition of a z-stack encompassing the depth of the capillary (Figure 2). Once tile acquisition is done, ZEN triggers the VAST software to either move to the next tile position or to the next larva. Acquisition can then be programmed for as many wells as necessary, each well containing up to 3 larvae. Loading the larvae from the well plate takes an average of thirty seconds per larva, while imaging takes an average of one minute per tile.

The number of tiles required per larva will depend on the area of interest, the objective (field of view), and larva age. When two or more tiles are necessary, an additional stitching step is required. Here we share a Python-based alternative to the ImageJ stitched script originally developed for this platform (Early et al., 2018). The original setup included a piezo objective scanner with a range limited to 400 μm, which required two consecutive stacks per tile to image the whole capillary (600-700 μm) and an initial concatenation step before stitching. We removed the piezo unit and took a single, long z-stack per tile, without a significant impact on acquisition times. We aimed to halve the number of stacks per tile to simplify data management and enable easier integration of the script into image analysis workflows.

Figure 2. Schematic showing the position of the capillary relative to the microscope objective. The capillary is inside a water-filled chamber with side windows toward the onboard camera (not shown). The microscope stage slides the capillary chamber along the x-axis to position the objective based on the distance from the tip of the head to the area of interest. Movement on the Y-axis is only possible manually.

The pipeline stitches the sequential tiles into a single 3D mosaic by assuming tiles are already co-registered in Y (no geometric alignment is performed) and placing them along X using a fixed, user-defined overlap fraction converted to a pixel step from each tile width. To infer whether the acquisition progressed left→right or right→left without reordering files, it compares both hypotheses by extracting the expected overlap edge strips from each neighbouring tile pair on a robust 2D projection (median over Z and, if present, median over channels), applying median-based gain normalization, and scoring similarity via mean absolute difference; the direction with the lower total mismatch is selected, with “reverse” implemented by growing the mosaic to the left while preserving file order. During compositing, each incoming tile is intensity-matched to the existing mosaic using the median intensity within the overlap (per-channel when applicable) and blended across the overlap using a linear feather ramp to reduce seam artifacts before copying the non-overlapping region directly into the output volume. This pipeline corrects intensity discontinuities at tile boundaries but does not perform geometric registration (e.g., drift/rotation/nonrigid alignment); it assumes consistent Z sampling and Y alignment across tiles.

In addition to the high-resolution confocal images, brightfield, whole-larva images can be captured using the VAST onboard camera. After the larva is detected and positioned, TIFF images with a 10- μm resolution are automatically taken of each larva at customizable viewing angles (Figure 3). These images can be used for quantitative evaluation of the morphological changes of larvae after chemical or genetic treatments. Such quantifications can be performed in ImageJ or other image analysis software. An excellent analysis tool specifically designed for images from the VAST onboard camera is the [FishInspector](#) software.

Figure 3. Images taken with the VAST Bioluminescence Imaging (VAST) onboard camera. It is possible to select several viewing angles per larva, although the lateral and dorsal views are the most useful. The pixel size of the on-board VAST camera is 5.5 x 5.5 μm .

Datasets

Datasets from two experiments were used to develop and test the new stitching script. The metadata is provided in a separate table following the Recommended Metadata for Biological Images (REMBI) guidelines, aiming to satisfy the FAIR principles (findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable) (Sarkans et al., 2021) (*Metadata_Python-based stitching script for Zebrafish screening*). The datasets named *Fli1-EGFP_4dpf_4tiles_...* contain four tiles per larva, which span their whole-body length, with a reporter for blood vessels. The datasets *NBT-DsRed_5fpf_3tiles_...* contain three tiles per larva, at higher resolution, spanning the area of interest after mechanical spinal cord lesioning in larvae expressing a neuronal reporter (Figure 4). Numerous zebrafish lines express fluorescent markers in different cell types and tissues, or are models for a diverse range of human diseases. Conducting preclinical screens in such zebrafish lines can help find molecules that can ultimately be used in clinical applications.

Figure 4. Example images showing the result of stitching the two image sets provided. Scale bar is 200 μ m.

To reduce imaging times, brightfield and fluorescence channels were acquired in separate z-stacks, called Acquisition blocks. The file name of the z-stacks in each block has the suffix *_AcquisitionBlock#_pt#*. Acquisition block 1 corresponds to the brightfield channel, and block 2 to the fluorescent channel. The part number (pt#) indicates the order in which the z-stack was acquired, and it's independent of the acquisition block. This suffix is predetermined for the Time Series mode in our version of the ZEN Software (version 2.6) and cannot be modified. On the other hand, the file name prefix is established by the user, so we suggest the naming convention: *<date>_<sampleID>_Block<channelID>_pt<tileIndex>.czi*

The VAST software generates a CSV (Comma-Separated Values) file containing the relevant experimental parameters (well, larva number per well, orientation, tile position, angle, and trigger time) from the imaging run. This file is very useful for correlating the z-stack with the larva and, consequently, with the treatments or conditions being compared in the screen.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I
1	Well	Fish	Orientation	X(micron)	Angle	DateTime out trigger	DateTime in signal	BF/AcqBlock 1_pt#	FL/AcqBlock 2_pt#
2	A01	1	tail	500	270	15 08 2025 16:37	15 08 2025 16:39	1	2
3	A01	1	tail	1500	270	15 08 2025 16:39	15 08 2025 16:40	3	4
4	A01	1	tail	2500	270	15 08 2025 16:40	15 08 2025 16:41	5	6
5	A01	1	tail	3500	270	15 08 2025 16:41	15 08 2025 16:42	7	8
6	A02	1	tail	500	270	15 08 2025 16:43	15 08 2025 16:45	9	10
7	A02	1	tail	1500	270	15 08 2025 16:45	15 08 2025 16:46	11	12
8	A02	1	tail	2500	270	15 08 2025 16:46	15 08 2025 16:47	13	14
9	A02	1	tail	3500	270	15 08 2025 16:47	15 08 2025 16:48	15	16
10	A03	1	tail	500	270	15 08 2025 16:49	15 08 2025 16:50	17	18

Figure 5. The VAST BioImager CSV contains essential metadata to identify each sample. ZEN is not integrated with the VAST software, so the only correlation between larva source and the confocal images is the time/order in which they were acquired.

Pre-processing of CZI stacks

There is an issue with the raw CZI files acquired with the triggered Time Series mode. When opened individually, they look incorrectly stitched, despite being unstitched single images (Figure 6). A macro for ZEN, called *Re-vast Files*, was written to fix the issue. The macro pre-processes the raw files, slightly reduces the file size of the stacks, and also generates a maximum intensity projection (MIP) of each one, necessary for the original stitching macro for ImageJ. The script for the ZEN software is available in the Files section. Images acquired manually do not have this issue and don't require pre-processing.

Figure 6. Pre-processing the files from the triggered Time Series acquisition mode from our ZEN software is necessary to ensure correct stitching. The examples for unprocessed CZI files are maximum intensity projections (MIP) of the z-stacks corresponding to the fluorescent and brightfield channels of a single tile. This issue with acquisition likely doesn't exist in different microscopy systems, but it is important to consider this step when establishing a workflow.

The datasets shared in this publication have been pre-processed with *Re-vast Files*. Raw files are available upon request.

Contact

If you are interested in testing the VAST-SDCM screening platform, feel free to contact Prof. [Catherina G. Becker](mailto:catherina.becker@tu-dresden.de) (catherina.becker@tu-dresden.de).

Acknowledgements

The authors thank Dr. [Riccardo Massei](#) (Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research (UFZ); NFDI4BIOIMAGE Data Steward) for his invaluable guidance on research data management for high-content screening (HCS). We also thank the [NFDI4BIOIMAGE](#) consortium, in particular Dr. [Cornelia Wetzker](#), for her support and expert advice, which were essential to this work.

References

- Pardo-Martin, C., Chang, T.-Y., Koo, B.K., Gilleland, C.L., Wasserman, S.C., Yanik, M.F., 2010. High-throughput in vivo vertebrate screening. *Nat Methods* 7, 634–636. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nmeth.1481>
- Chang, T.-Y., Pardo-Martin, C., Allalou, A., Wählby, C., Yanik, M.F., 2012. Fully automated cellular-resolution vertebrate screening platform with parallel animal processing. *Lab Chip* 12, 711–716. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C1LC20849G>
- Oprışoreanu, A.-M., Smith, H.L., Krix, S., Chaytow, H., Carragher, N.O., Gillingwater, T.H., Becker, C.G., Becker, T., 2021. Automated in vivo drug screen in zebrafish identifies synapse-stabilising drugs with relevance to spinal muscular atrophy. *Disease Models & Mechanisms* 14, dmm047761. <https://doi.org/10.1242/dmm.047761>

Early, J.J., Marshall-Phelps, K.L., Williamson, J.M., Swire, M., Kamadurai, H., Muskavitch, M., Lyons, D.A., 2018. An automated high-resolution in vivo screen in zebrafish to identify chemical regulators of myelination. *eLife* 7, e35136. <https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.35136>

Sarkans, U., Chiu, W., Collinson, L. et al., 2021. REMBI: Recommended Metadata for Biological Images—enabling reuse of microscopy data in biology. *Nat Methods* 18, 1418–1422. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41592-021-01166-8>